

Hoppa:

Tackling information overload
in the built environment sector

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THE ALAN TURING INSTITUTE CASE STUDY

Hoppa:

Tackling information overload in the built environment sector

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Topic overview

This case study explores how information management technology company Hoppa is applying responsible AI to address one of the most persistent challenges in the built environment sector: the inability to find and act on important information relating to assets such as buildings or infrastructure. By automating the organisation, classification and governance of asset data, Hoppa helps infrastructure owners and their supply chains get the most out of stored information and reduce associated risks – producing a significant positive shift in how the industry applies digital insights in the real world.

Figure 1: The Hoppa ecosystem enables built environment teams to transform messy documents and data into structured, reliable information they can actually use.
Image credit: Hoppa.ai

The costs of hard-to-find built environment data

Across the built environment, vast amounts of information are created over the lifecycle of an asset: drawings, specifications, inspection reports, invoices, operational records and more. This information is critical to safety, compliance, cost control, and long-term asset performance and evaluation. Yet in practice, the information is often fragmented, poorly labelled, in non-compatible formats, and difficult to retrieve. Even routine audits and maintenance planning can take months as teams manually search across digital estates for the data they need.

For major infrastructure owners, this is more than just an efficiency problem. In emergency situations – such as a fire, a system failure, or even a lorry getting stuck under a bridge – delays in locating accurate information can put lives at risk and lead to prolonged asset downtime.

Hoppa was created to address this problem (the name is a play on ‘hopper’, a funnel-like machine used in the construction industry to separate different types of material – or in Hoppa’s case, data). Led by founders Tom Goldsmith and Sam Rees, both experienced civil engineers, the company works with asset owners and suppliers to apply AI and automation to information governance. Their aim is not simply to make documents easier to find and search, but to fundamentally change how information is structured, distributed and accessed across complex supply chains.

Participation in BridgeAI, in particular The Turing Way Practitioners Hub delivered by The Alan Turing Institute, has helped Hoppa frame its work within broader principles of open data governance, responsible AI and human oversight, as well as shining a light on the ways in which careful technological advancement can improve practices for the sector as a whole.

Too much information: When volume outgrows human capacity

The built environment produces information continuously, often over decades. As Tom explains, a drawing created in the 2010s may need to be located and interpreted by someone working on the same asset 40 years later – a task that traditional information management approaches struggle to predict and facilitate.

Figure 2: Information loss and recovery introduces costs and inefficiencies at every lifecycle stage. **Image credit:** Hoppa.ai

In many organisations, critical data is stored across multiple systems and formats, from PDFs and spreadsheets to computer-aided design (CAD) drawings and photographs. While common data environments have improved governance and traceability, they remain heavily dependent on human effort to find, interpret, and classify documents.

As data volumes grow, this approach becomes unsustainable, and even well-resourced organisations face severe capacity constraints. The result is an industry that often accepts poor information quality, preferring to commission new asset surveys, or layer in additional contingency that impacts cost and schedule.

Figure 3: Hoppa’s simple four-step process can be applied to any built environment data transformation use case. **Image credit:** Hoppa.ai

Hoppa addresses this problem by applying automation to tasks that have previously relied entirely on human effort. Tom describes the platform as an “information management automation layer” that helps teams catalogue, govern, and exchange information across the built asset lifecycle. The system’s impact is huge: Hoppa’s automated data labelling can be carried out up to 500 times faster than manual labelling.

A ‘data refinery’ for the industry – with humans in the loop

Figure 4: Indexing files from a source SharePoint site using the Hoppa web app is secure by design; file streaming during analysis ensures Hoppa’s customers retain custody of information. **Image credit:** Hoppa.ai

Rather than acting as a separate data repository, Hoppa sits on top of existing systems, using AI techniques such as optical character recognition, inductive reasoning and vector search to analyse documents in situ and apply consistent metadata aligned to each customer’s organisational structure. Sam characterises this approach as being like a data refinery for the industry: transforming vast quantities of raw, unstructured information into data that can be reliably searched and used.

Figure 5: Hoppa's AI-generated confidence scores and supporting rationale ensure responsible human oversight of AI. **Image credit:** Hoppa.ai

While automation is central to this approach, human oversight remains crucial. The system flags uncertainty, allowing high-confidence classifications to be accepted quickly while directing ambiguous cases for human review. This human-in-the-loop principle ensures that people retain agency in the quality control process and allows the system to improve over time through human-led corrections. And the directed and contextualised process means human review can now take place in a fraction of the time.

For Hoppa, this balance is a core principle of responsible AI: using automation to reduce administrative burden and improve reliability, while ensuring that decision-making and responsibility are not handed over completely to a computer.

Real-world examples of the Hoppa system in action

A UK international airport: planning maintenance proactively

Working alongside engineering consultancy AtkinsRéalis, the challenge was to implement a cutting-edge predictive maintenance approach for the road network at a major UK international airport. To move towards a proactive rather than reactive maintenance model, AtkinsRéalis needed to establish when assets were constructed, what materials were used, and how long components were expected to last.

This information existed across an enormous number of documents in different formats and was, in effect, largely inaccessible. Using Hoppa's platform, tens of thousands of documents were analysed and narrowed down to a much smaller subset that contained the relevant information. Engineers could then focus their efforts on validating and using that data, rather than searching for it.

Figure 6: Hoppa identified and extracted facts from drawings, handwritten notes, engineering reports and more. **Image credit:** Hoppa.ai

Reflecting on the project, AtkinsRéalis Associate Director Quintin Viljoen said: “While engineering judgment remains essential for interpretation, Hoppa transforms desktop workflows, optimises resource utilisation, and reduces potential unnecessary intrusive site investigations. It is strongly recommended that Hoppa be adopted as a core component of desktop analysis to maximise efficiency, lower costs, and enable data-driven decision-making across the network.”

What would previously have required an infeasible number of person-hours to carry out became achievable in a fraction of the time, realising the airport’s vision of site-wide predictive maintenance planning.

HS2: reducing risk in financial oversight

A different application using the same technology emerged at the high-speed rail network HS2, where the organisation processes around 10,000 supply chain invoices per month but, like many organisations, has capacity to verify only a small proportion manually. This creates a risk that disallowable costs – and potentially fraudulent claims – go undetected.

HS2 asked Hoppa to apply its classification and labelling technology to help identify which invoices merited deeper scrutiny. Early proof-of-value work has shown that AI-driven classification can help teams focus their limited capacity where it is needed most, improving financial control without increasing headcount or workload.

HS2’s progressive, AI-assisted approach to cost control sets a new benchmark for major capital delivery in a sector that has to date tolerated such challenges.

Implementing learnings from The Turing Way Practitioners Hub

Participation in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has provided Hoppa with a structured space to reflect on the wider implications of its AI-based product development. Discussions around ethics, governance, and stakeholder engagement have reinforced the importance of designing AI systems that augment human capability rather than replace it, as demonstrated by the company's commitment to human-in-the-loop principles.

The Practitioners Hub has also supported Hoppa in framing its work as part of a broader shift in industry practice. As AI reduces the cost of information governance, it creates a new obligation: organisations can no longer justify poor data management as unavoidable. Instead, continuous, proactive information governance becomes both feasible and expected. Tom and Sam also note that more reliable information governance can support longer asset lifespans and more informed decisions around reuse and decarbonisation, which is important in the context of national infrastructure sustainability priorities.

Another key element of responsible AI implementation explored as part of the Practitioners Hub is ensuring data security. In highly regulated built environments, nuclear infrastructure, for instance, security concerns often mean stakeholders are locked out of all data – even when they only need access to a small subset. Technological advances such as Hoppa's AI-driven platform allow companies to apply more granular security controls, enabling suppliers to collaborate more closely and access the information they need without exposing the wider data estate to unacceptable risk.

Challenges and next steps: demonstrating value and moving towards responsible agentic AI

Information governance in the built environment is shaped by legacy tools, systems, processes and standards. Changing these practices requires not just the right technology, but also – amid potential cynicism towards the adoption of new digital tools – trust, cultural change, and clear demonstration of value. Hoppa is working on this challenge through proof-of-value and benchmarking studies, as well as customer testimonials, that show evidence of real-world impact and the practical benefits of AI-enabled information management.

Alongside this, Tom and Sam are continuing to refine the platform's flexibility and interoperability, ensuring it can adapt to different organisational contexts. The emphasis remains on acting as an integration and automation layer that complements existing systems, rather than replacing them. Hoppa is pioneering a virtual knowledge layer, whereby files are indexed and mapped into the master metadata catalogue while the file itself remains in the source custody of the owner.

Looking further ahead, Hoppa is exploring how the structured, machine-readable information produced through its current approach could support more advanced, agentic AI use cases. This includes the possibility of AI systems not only retrieving information for humans, but acting on that information within defined guardrails. The team is clear that such future capabilities must be rooted in robust governance procedures, human oversight, and explainability.

Reflections on *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub

“The Practitioners Hub has been valuable in helping us step back from the technology and think about the wider system we’re operating in: how information moves around, where responsibility sits, and how AI can support people working in the sector rather than replacing them. That perspective is really important as we look to scale the business. At the BridgeAI Adopters and Developers event in particular, we were able to have balanced conversations not just about risk, but about how AI can be applied responsibly to mitigate the risks and solve real problems in our various sectors.”

Tom Goldsmith,
Co-Founder, Hoppa.ai

Key takeaways

- Poor information governance in the built environment sector creates safety, compliance, financial and resourcing risks that can be managed and reduced with the help of AI.
- AI enables information management at volumes and speeds that may be infeasible with human effort alone. The biggest opportunities are often in designing interoperable platforms that sit on top of existing systems, rather than introducing standalone new tools.
- Human-in-the-loop design is essential for the responsible implementation of AI in safety-critical settings.
- Lowering the cost of data classification through technological advances can drive improvements within information-heavy industries such as the construction sector and enable secure, more selective data sharing across supply chains.
- AI works best – and is easiest to pitch to end users – when applied successfully to real-world problems. Reliability, repeatability and utility always beat flashiness and “AI for the sake of AI”.
- AI should be seen as an opportunity and not just talked about in the context of its risks. While careful consideration of safety and ethics is essential, an overly negative framing can obscure AI’s potential to address longstanding challenges and improve outcomes in traditional sectors.

Contributors and acknowledgements

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This case study is published under ***The Turing Way Practitioners Hub*** 2025–26 Cohort – case study series. The Practitioners Hub is ***The Turing Way*** project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Tom Goldsmith and Sam Rees from Hoppa.ai**, as Experts-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI, as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

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With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, BridgeAI aims to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub’s 2025–26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher – Open Source Practices and **Dr Ann Borda**, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager and the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of ‘Experts in Residence’ across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: theturingway@gmail.com

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